

Towards a cellulose-based society: Demonstrating the feasibility of new bio-based material concepts and products

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Abstract In moving towards a cellulose-based society, interdisciplinary effort is required as it is at this interface that new ideas are found and can grow. New bio-based materials will play a key role but getting them into the marketplace is not always straightforward. Many options are available both for sourcing and for producing composite materials from wood-based cellulose and poly-lactic acid (PLA). Depending on how the material is processed, a multitude of properties can be generated. The main goal with this work was to attempt to reduce the research-to-market gap. This was done by testing a new way of working together where we bundled innovation-oriented projects and research-oriented projects around the theme of material experience. We then systematically worked with material demonstrators. In this article, we exemplify the results by focusing on one research-oriented project that did not at the outset have a market context and on one innovation-oriented project with clear market requirements. In addition to introducing a new concept in bundling research-oriented and innovation-oriented projects, this paper contributes several practical examples of what material demonstrators can do. We also present an application and analysis of Moultrie's extended Science-Technology-Application-Market (STAM) model to analyze the material demonstrators and design phases of the bundled projects. We modified the proposed classification with different types of material demonstrators according to how close they are to an actual product segment. Designers and scientists worked together but with different emphasis in each phase.

Keywords *Bio-based materials, Demonstrators, Design, Experience, STAM model*

Introduction

As science and technology continue to move forward towards renewable and more environmentally friendly materials and processes, interdisciplinary effort is required in order to achieve groundbreaking research in material and product development (Golembiewski et.al. 2015) 'The bio-based economy can and should be to the 21st century what the fossil-based economy was to the 20th century' according to Hardy (Hardy 2002, p.11). This statement emphasizes not only the relevance of the bio economy for both academia and industry but the need for research efforts to join different disciplines. Bio-based materials are central to implementing a bio-based economy. Cellulose is the most abundant organic polymer on earth (Klemm et.al. 2005) and one of the most promising renewable source materials to replace commodity plastics is Polylactic acid (PLA).

PLA is a biodegradable plastic made from starch that combined with wood pulp creates a material that acquires new properties when heated. PLA fibers and wood pulp fibers are commingled to produce a generic

paper multi-material, where distinctively different properties can be enhanced depending on the processing and converting stages. The ratio of pulp to PLA can be varied and the material can be produced on a full-scale pilot paper machine or extruded, hot pressed or injection molded. Different applications can be created, e.g. clothing applications by creping and pleating the material or boards by using hot pressing (Granberg et al., 2015).

The structure in the material will define the material properties. Relevant material properties can be tailored by designing the components (e.g. designing the fibre), the composition of components (e.g. component blends, fibre properties and orientations etc.) and the product property requirements. Lindström (Lindström et.al. 2014) calls this approach hierarchic design and points out the importance of interdisciplinary translation and cooperation between material scientists and designers. In this model, the component design level is dominated by scientists and influenced by the designer, while the product design stage is mostly dominated by designers but still with

Figure 1. Pulp-PLA composite produced on paper machine and creped (left), injection molded (middle), and 3D printed (right).

the input of scientists. The steps between these see designers and scientists working together, iterating between the different possible realisations of each step and narrowing in on the way forward.

Introducing new materials, especially if they have new properties, can be a lengthy process. There is a need for better understanding how to systematically explore new bio-based materials. This type of exploration usually entails some form of material swatches, demonstrators and even early product-level prototyping which can be used to communicate about the material. This article describes some methods for exploring new materials and then classifying the demonstrators to better understand how to decrease the research-to-market gap.

Methods

The materials in focus were made from cellulose and PLA. Some examples are shown in Figure 1. They exemplify the span of how different materials made from these components can be. They also show the different processing methods that are possible.

Meaning of materials

One of the keys to the commercial success of new bio-plastic materials is that they be introduced with unique aesthetic properties emphasizing that they are different to the ones currently on the marketplace (Karana, 2012; Karana et.al. 2015). New forest-based renewable composites should thus not only fulfil technical requirements, they should also appeal to users' senses and render an intended meaning to products. Material experience combines the ways in which we perceive a material via our senses and through associations with its physical properties (Jonsson et.al. 2008; Karana, 2012; Karana et.al. 2009; Lindberg et.al. 2013). Many factors affect the way a material is perceived: how it is processed, the product it is embodied in, when it is used, and the background of the user, i.e. culture, gender, previous experiences etc. (Karana et.al. 2010).

TechMark Arena

In order to explore new ways to communicate the principles of materials science to a non-scientific audience and bridge the research-to-market gap for new bio-based materials, the TechMark Arena was launched. It is structured as a program where research-oriented master's projects are bundled and

run in teams with innovation-oriented master's projects (Béland et.al. 2015). The eight students were from three different universities and were supervised by a team of five researchers. By combining material scientists with students from different disciplines, a new way to test the pathway of new material concepts from the lab to the marketplace was explored. Instead of running individual master's projects on specific questions, several master's students were coordinated to address a common theme from different perspectives. For the 2015 program the theme was new bio-based materials related to material experience and market potential. The projects included in 2015 are briefly presented here.

1. Stimuli-responsive degradation of a textile-like pulp/PLA material modified by polyelectrolyte assembly. (Research-oriented project)

The constantly new and changing fashion industry combined with sales and cheap garments are highly influencing factors dominating the fast quantitative usage of apparel in the Western world. Carried out by chemistry student Tove Kristensen, from KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Kristensen, 2015), the project evaluated an alternative to developing clothes that will last forever. Instead, manufacturing biocomposite fabrics on a paper machine and incorporating a stimuli-induced degradation process creates a "fast fashion" alternative. Garments are used for 1-5 days and then degrade when composted. The project was designed as a pre-study for a broader project which attempts to examine the vision of a deliberate degradation process of textile-like PLA/wood fibre material triggered by the body during use.

2. Material Identity Crisis: Tailoring the properties of a material showing its potential through a demonstrator. (Research-oriented project)

The title Material Identity Crisis was chosen as it brings together the two crucial parts of the project. The fact that the material is a new bio-based material creates a material identity crisis in itself. Textile-like PLA-paper does not necessarily belong to any of the traditional groups of materials. Another perspective on a material identity crisis is to stress a material's properties for it to be perceived in different ways. Carried out by product development and design students Anna Nilsson and Hanna Skoglund from Linköping University (Nilsson & Skoglund, 2015), a material-driven product development process was

used to explore the behaviour of textile-like PLA-paper for a packaging solution.

3. Economics/added-value of bio-based materials from the forest (Research-oriented project)

The aim was to investigate the bio-based added value of bio-based packaging and packaging materials. Economics student Karl Berntsson, SLU, the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, investigated possible competitive advantages of bio-based alternatives, willingness to pay for and the ability to obtain a green price premium for bio-based materials and products. Preliminary results (the thesis is not yet registered) indicate that there is added value linked to bio-based materials and products that is not found in corresponding petroleum-based materials and products.

4. Possibilities and limitations for a bio-based composite to be used as speaker cabinet material (Innovation-oriented project)

A producer of high quality speaker cabinets was looking for alternatives to medium-density fibreboard (MDF), to make production of their cabinets faster, cheaper and more environmentally friendly. Industrial product development student Benoît Coste, KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Coste, 2015) evaluated the possibility offered by bio-composites containing pulp fibres, like more shaping options, faster manufacturing than MDF, possibility to process by injection moulding, and reduced impact on the environment compared to fossil-based plastics. A functional user-centred speaker cabinet prototype was made and its production feasibility investigated.

5. Next Generation of Active Underwear - Implementing Smart Textiles and Technologies (Innovation-oriented project)

Active Underwear is underwear aimed at sports applications. The demand for smart textiles and technologies is predicted to increase but it is not always obvious how to make best use of available solutions. Industrial product development students Elin Cadenius and Kim Gartvall, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, in collaboration with Björn Borg (Cadenius & Gartvall, 2015), developed new innovative and sustainable concepts for doing just this. They also mapped relevant textiles and technologies implementable in sports underwear. The project compared a number of commercially used sportswear textiles with a number of newer textiles made from natural fibres.

6. Bio-based Clothes Covers for a High-end Clothing Brand (Innovation-oriented project)

There is a growing interest in using plastics from renewable resources and other bio-based materials to replace conventional fossil-based plastics. New clothes covers intended for hanging clothes (primarily suits) also needed to be compatible in the current transport chain, be aesthetically appealing, and add value by being used by end-users as a transport bag. Industrial product development student Sebastian de Arteaga, KTH Royal Institute of Technology (de Arteaga, 2015) worked in collaboration with Tiger of Sweden. A large number of suitable bio-based materials were

evaluated. Two concepts were generated for the brand based on commercially available bio-based polyethylene, and a more long-term compostable concept was investigated that used bio-based materials combining PLA, wood-based fibres and nanocellulose.

Technology Readiness Level and STAM

The framework of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) as defined by NASA is increasingly used as a way to categorize technological development and to classify research and innovation, e.g. by the European Commission. Moultrie (Moultrie, 2015) examined the role of demonstrators in scientific activity and classified them according to the Science, Technology, Application, Market (STAM) framework. TRL can be mapped onto STAM but STAM is broader in scope and covers the whole span from scientific discovery to commercialisation. Of interest for analysing our demonstrators is that the STAM framework also contains a proposal of different types of demonstrators aligned with the model. We use Moultrie's extended STAM model that includes Science, Technology, Future Application, Specific Application, and Potential Market as the phases of progression. The purpose of the classification is to help understand the role of demonstrators in the research-to-market process.

Results and discussion

User's sensory perception and appraisal of material/product was a common denominator in 4 of the 6 projects and the studies performed addressed different levels of material perception and meaning. Sensorial properties as well as affective attributes were evaluated to different degrees depending on closeness to the market. Some of the investigated attributes were used within several projects. An overview of the attributes is shown in Table 1. The materials developed in the research-oriented projects were also included in some of the studies of the innovation-oriented projects. This made it possible to compare the new materials with existing materials for specific applications, while conducting studies without context.

The research-oriented projects focused on the development of new materials and how their properties could be explored and communicated. In these projects, the focus was to understand how the material could be formulated and processed to be suitable for different applications and to generate different perceptual responses for the users.

The innovation-oriented projects had a pre-defined market context with the specific issues having been defined by collaborating companies. These projects included investigations of both existing and new materials in the context of specific market applications. The focus was to identify materials that, in addition to possessing the required technical properties, were perceived in ways consistent with the brand and desirable for the applications.

The TechMark Arena 2015 projects were defined with starting points either focused on the potential (new)

uses of new bio-based materials or on specific market segments requiring the investigation and use of new bio-based alternatives to existing materials. All projects, except project 3 that analyzed economics, focused on material development, exploration and application possibilities. The approximate fit of the projects with the different STAM phases is shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Sensorial and affective attributes investigated in four of the projects.

Attributes	TechMark Arena Project			
	2 (Material identity crisis)	4 (Speaker Cabinets)	5 (Smart textiles)	6 (Clothes covers)
Affective				
Luxurious	X			X
Masculine				X
Modern		X		X
Premium				X
Unique	X	X		X
Lively	X			
Natural	X	X		
Fun	X	X		
Expensive	X	X		
Extravagant	X	X		
High quality	X	X	X	
Playful	X			
Serious	X			
Eco-friendly		X		
Furniture-like		X		
Ugly		X		
Minimalistic		X		
Professional		X		
Comfortable			X	
Sporty			X	
Textile-like	X			
Paper-like	X			
Sensorial				
Soft	X		X	
Smooth	X		X	
Matte	X			
Reflective	X			
Cold/cool	X		X	
Elastic	X			
Opaque	X			
Ductile	X			
Strong	X			
Light	X			
Good breathability			X	
Good support			X	
Stays dry			X	

Within the TechMark Arena, material development was carried out both in context, as for the innovation-oriented projects dealing with clothes covers, smart textiles, and speaker cabinets, and without context, as in the research-oriented material identity crisis project. Those projects that started with the market segment already defined led to both proposed solutions for immediate implementation and to solutions that in the longer term could take advantage of new bio-based materials.

In other words, the projects' focus started in the potential market phase and evolved into concepts requiring technology development. Regardless of whether the projects were carried out in context or without; demonstrators were an important part of the process for all projects. The types ranged from abstract demonstrators at laboratory scale showing technical possibilities, to both future and specific application demonstrators for well-defined market segments. When a project started with newly developed materials and the aim was to explore potential avenues for using the material, demonstrators tended to start with the science and technology phases and move towards the market phase.

It is out of scope to present results from all projects. In the next sections, we highlight the results of one research-oriented project that did not at the outset have a market context and one innovation-oriented project with clear market requirements.

Creating a design concept using the MoM tool – research-oriented project case

The project Material Identity Crisis (Nilsson & Skoglund, 2015) revolved around textile-like pulp-PLA paper in combination with creping, heat treatment, and folding in order to control both form freedom and experience properties of a new multilateral. We expand on this case as a research-oriented project.

The expected outcome was a demonstrator that utilises the advantages of textile-like materials and possible conversion techniques. Two different meanings were selected, namely *Luxurious* and *Playful*. Using the Meaning of Material (MoM) Survey

Table 2. TechMark Arena projects that dealt with materials and their approximate fit to the different extended STAM phases.

Project fit with STAM phases*	STAM phases				
	Science	Technology	Future Application	Specific Application	Potential Market
1 (Chemistry)	100%				
2 (Material identity crisis)		70%	20%	10%	
4 (Speaker cabinets)		20%	20%	60%	
5 (Smart textiles)			20%	80%	
6 (Clothes covers)			30%	60%	10%

* Project 3 was not technological in nature and is not included here.

Figure 2. Examples of uploaded images of Luxurious (left) and Playful (right).

proposed by Karana (Karana et al., 2010) 73 respondents gave an example of a material they thought was *Luxurious* (n=36), and one they thought of as *Playful* (n=37). Respondents also uploaded a picture of the material embodied in a product, explained why they thought the material was luxurious or playful and then rated the chosen material on a sensorial scale.

The results showed that materials perceived as *Luxurious* are *smooth, glossy, not elastic and strong*. The uploaded pictures showed materials that can be divided in two groups; soft materials dominated by fabrics (notably silk) and hard materials dominated by metals and minerals. The majority of the pictures featured materials with a smooth finish. Some participants wrote that a rare or unique material is luxurious.

Materials perceived as *Playful* are *soft, smooth, opaque, ductile and light*. The uploaded pictures showed materials in industrially mass produced products with several colours, many embodied in a product that had been manufactured through moulding. The uploaded pictures (Figure 2) show examples of luxurious and playful materials embedded in products.

The Materials Identity Crisis project also produced a number of material demonstrators. These were classified as abstract, conceptual, or “productified” (Béland & Granberg 2015) depending on how close they were to an actual product segment.

Abstract demonstrators were created based on the results of the MoM survey in order to understand the effect of process parameters on material perception (Table 3, rows 1-2). Batches of the textile-like PLA-paper were produced and processed using different dye types and nip pressures. Karana refers to this step as “tinkering with the material” (Karana et.al. 2015). The resulting demonstrators were evaluated on the sensorial scales from the MoM survey with a different (new) group of respondents (n=23). The results showed that the material samples were perceived as opaque, non-reflective, light weight,

tough, matte and ductile. In addition, samples were also compared for the selected meanings, *Luxurious* and *Playful*, by placing them on a 2-dimensional visual analogue scale with orthogonal axes.

Nilsson & Skoglund (2015) then compared how the material demonstrators performed with respect to the desired material properties from the initial MoM-survey. It was found that the desired playful properties could be fulfilled with the textile-like PLA-paper as long as the right samples were chosen. The desired luxurious properties were less fulfilled by the material as is and further conversion could achieve the desired properties. Heat treatment was tried as way of altering both the material properties and the material expression in the desired directions. This work led to the abstract demonstrator depicted on the second row in Table 3.

Based on the results from the MoM-survey design guidelines were established as a starting point for the development of two demonstrators. These included recommendations regarding for example shape, color, patterns and surfaces. Beverage packaging was selected as the application and it was decided that two different demonstrators would be developed, one expressing *Playful* and one expressing *Luxury*.

Conceptual demonstrators were produced to show both potential contexts for use and the different ways the material can be processed and converted. From this, more concrete sketches were made before testing different variations in 2D mock-ups (Table 3, rows 3 and 5). These served as the basis for discussion in a workshop and helped narrow down the possibilities for the visualization stage of the project (Table 3, rows 4 and 6). The conceptual demonstrators played a critical role in invention, serving both to communicate material properties and ideas for potential use as well as inspiring entirely new materials. One invention disclosure came out of the process, followed by an application to patent.

Productified 3D demonstrators were the last to be produced in the project and expressed the two very different attributes of *Luxury* and *Playful* in the

Figure 3. Visualization of the mean scores given to the luxurious (left) and playful (right) champagne packaging concepts. Black lines and dark blue circles show significant results.

context of packaging for a champagne bottle (Table 3, last row). The material is processed and converted to show a possible use within this market segment and a final perception study was performed in order to find out if the intended attributes were being expressed. The study was made through a survey based on the semantic differential method (Krippendorff & Butter 1984). Apart from the attributes *Luxurious* and *Playful*, some complementary adjective pairs of interest were investigated. Twenty-six respondents participated in this study. The luxurious concept was considered to be significantly ($p < 0.5$) serious, unique, extravagant, calm, expensive and high quality (Figure 3, left). There were many positive comments about the design but it was also stated that the perception of the material as exclusive and luxurious was hindered by its tactile properties and the lack of preciseness in the execution of the demonstrator. The playful concept was considered to be significantly ($p < 0.5$) playful, lively, unique, artificial, cheerful, fun, extravagant, cheap and not luxurious (Figure 3, right).

In moving from the Science STAM phase towards the Potential Market STAM phase, the type of material demonstrator changes from abstract, to conceptual to “productified” but not necessarily in a linear fashion. This indicates that RDI demonstrators are iterative in their nature. Identifying the best type of demonstrator to produce requires that it be placed in a relevant context. This helped us in identifying potential market segments for which new materials are needed, either by modifying the materials demonstrators developed within the projects or by developing completely new materials.

Creating a design concept for an innovation-oriented project case

We present here partial results from project 6, Bio-based Clothes Covers for a High-end Clothing Brand. In this project a material experience study was performed as part of the material selection process. The study was made with two different test groups; one group with respondent from the general public (potential consumers) and one test group consisting of staff at the company (designers, purchasers, production coordinators etc.). In total 28 respondents participated in the study.

The participants were asked to evaluate 13 different

samples regarding 5 different attributes (see Table 1). The given context was materials for clothes covers. The material samples were chosen based on their abilities to fulfil the technical requirements for the application and consisted of both opaque and transparent materials, e.g. plastics, plastic films, paper/board and textile-like composite materials. The textile-like Pulp/PLA material investigated in the research-oriented projects was also included among the samples. This gave us the opportunity to explore how this new material performed compared to existing materials within this specific context.

The results showed that a black, shiny, non-elastic polyester fabric performed well for many of the attributes. For the attribute *Luxurious* this material scored high in both groups. This result agrees well with the results from the MoM-survey performed in the Material identity Crisis project which showed that materials perceived as *Luxurious* are smooth, glossy, not elastic and strong. However, the textile-like pulp/PLA sample was ranked the most luxurious, unique and premium by the consumer group. This also agrees with the final perception study performed in the Material identity Crisis project where both concepts were considered as significantly unique. For the plastic materials, the sample that scored highest was a two-sided matte/glossy 170 μm thick polyethylene film. Many respondent stated that stiffer and thicker plastic materials are more luxurious and of higher quality. Several respondents disliked the plastic samples that wrinkled. Opaque plastics were preferred over transparent; several respondents stated that transparent plastic was perceived as cheap, especially if it was hazy. The results were similar for the paper materials, the thicker samples performed better than the thin ones.

When comparing the results between the two test groups some differences could be identified. Some materials that were ranked lower by the company staff were preferred by the consumer group. One reason could be that the company staff had a deeper knowledge of the materials and therefore were more critical. It could also be that they were biased in that they recognized some of the materials. However, none of the groups showed significant opposite results where a sample scored significantly above average for one group but under average for the other.

Table 3. Material demonstrators of the Material Identity Crisis project, approximate fit with the STAM phases, and whether they were mainly the result of the work of the scientists (S), designers (D), or a collaborative effort.

Science	Technology	Future Application	Specific Application	Potential Market	Material Identity Crisis project: Material demonstrators in chronological order
	◆	◆			<p>Abstract demonstrators showing first color swatches of the new material</p> <p>S</p>
	◆	◆			<p>Abstract demonstrators showing color change after heat treatment</p> <p>S</p>
		◆	◆		<p>Visualizing scenarios of use</p> <p>D</p>
	◆	◆			<p>Conceptual demonstrators showing conversion techniques</p> <p>S, D</p>
			◆		<p>Sketches to illustrate possible concepts</p> <p>D</p>
			◆		<p>Conceptual demonstrators representing small-scale 2D design mock-ups</p> <p>D</p>
			◆	◆	<p>“Productified” 3D demonstrators expressing luxurious and playful for a given product segment</p> <p>S, D</p>

(S=Scientists, D=Designers)

◆ ◆ ◆ the larger the diamond the more relevant to the STAM phase

Figure 4. Two of the concepts from the Bio-based Clothes Covers project, one immediately implementable (left) and one medium to long-term future concept realizable within 2-5 years (right) requires development of the bio-based materials proposed.

The project produced a number of concepts, one that was investigated for commercial production by the company. In addition to concepts that were immediately possible, a number of concepts that utilized materials under development were also suggested. These would be made from fully bio-based materials, but required a certain level of development in terms of large scale production to be available to the company. Figure 4 shows the immediately implementable concept and the material demonstrator for the fully bio-based material concept available in the medium to long-term future (2-5 years).

Conclusions

The TechMark Arena 2015 increased our knowledge about bio-based materials and how they are experienced. Eight students focused on this theme from different perspectives. We were able to benchmark new bio-based materials against materials being used in the marketplace for different applications. One material group was used to benchmark the opinions of the experts in a market segment against those of consumers not working in this area.

Material demonstrators are an important part of the process of exploring what new materials can do and how they can be designed into products. Abstract demonstrators were used as a means to assess the effect of different processing steps. It is important to align material tactile and visual properties with desired properties as early on as possible. We found the MoM method to be useful in guiding the development of material demonstrators. Conceptual demonstrators served to communicate material properties and ideas for potential use and inspired one invention disclosure that became a patent application. Productified demonstrators elicited positive comments about product design but can also be used to communicate limitations and improvement potential of both the material and its processing. Demonstrators showed the utility of establishing an iterative process from the start. They also allowed the student and supervisory teams to benefit from having something tangible at the center of their discussions

and discovery. The classification of the material demonstrators in different STAM phases allowed us to assess the roles of scientists and designers in bridging the research-to-market gap.

Initially, we considered TRLs to be rather straightforward, with research-oriented projects falling on the low end (TRL 2-3) and innovation-oriented projects falling on the high end (around TRL 7-8). From the projects exemplified here, the research-oriented Material Identity Crisis project produced some results that had a higher TRL: a patent application with materials tested in laboratory environment, TRL 4. This happened much faster than we would have anticipated. Furthermore, the innovation-oriented Bio-based Clothes Covers project produced some concepts having a lower TRL (future demonstrator using fully bio-based materials, TRL 5 due to development need). This established concrete market needs for material development, also sooner than we anticipated. We found that by concentrating on a common theme, bundling research-oriented and innovation-oriented projects created synergies that were unforeseen, including a vaguely defined pipeline for future development of bio-based materials. This implies that given the right framework, the research-to-market gap can be decreased as a result of faster testing in a lab environment coupled with identification of future market needs for specific materials. The benefits of bundling research-oriented and innovation-oriented projects will be further investigated in upcoming TechMark Arenas.

The teams were multidisciplinary on both sides with supervisors working in areas ranging from psychology and material development to industrial design and innovation. Students came from four different institutions at three universities. We believe it was this interaction on many fronts that led to the successful outcome of the TechMark Arena. New bio-based materials will be crucial in the bioeconomy. Understanding them and how material demonstrators can be used to show potential applications will make the research-to-market gap a little narrower. The development and demonstration of new bio-based material concepts and products was iterative and therefore the process benefits from the interaction of scientists and designers knowledgeable in different disciplines.

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